

#19

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

**EVALUATOR SELF-ASSESSMENT:
UNCONSCIOUS BIAS**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Periodically throughout the interactive innovation process.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Evaluator self-assessment (one person) & discussion groups of 3 actors.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical expertise required, although this tool can be challenging if the user isn't familiar with the topic of unconscious bias.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Implemented periodically.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>No resources required, apart from basic materials.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 2, 3, 5, 6, 19, 20.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc.

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Self-assess for unconscious bias.
- Take actions to avoid unconscious bias.

Background and Logic

The success of multi-actor work depends on the quality of diversity in a group. The quality of diversity is determined by the actors who become (and are invited to be) involved, and the range of stakeholders engaged by a project. While other tools in this handbook (e.g. Tool #5 and Tool #6) are targeted at supporting meaningful inclusion of an appropriate diversity of actors/ stakeholders (by discovering and responding to different needs and motivations), this tool challenges actors leading and involved in multi-actor work to think critically about their biases.

Materials

- Online tools to learn about unconscious bias and to self assess for unconscious bias: available [here](#) & [here](#)
- Persona template
- Storyboarding template
- Reflective diary.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

The challenge of reducing unconscious bias is two-fold: raising awareness of the unconscious biases that people have; and taking actions to reduce unconscious bias. Harvard University provides useful resources for both. Aside from reading material, a comprehensive [podcast](#) debates the challenges of uncovering and addressing unconscious biases. In addition, Harvard's [Project Implicit](#) provides multiple tools for self-assessing unconscious biases.

In this tool, we set out some of the key learnings from these resources that are particularly relevant to interactive innovation and the multi-actor approach. We identify practical approaches for end-users in interactive innovation projects, which are suitable for enhancing the use of other tools in this handbook.

1. Assessing Actor/Role ID for Unconscious Bias

Tool#2 in this handbook presents how to assign tasks according to the different (sometimes unique) knowledges of different actors in the interactive innovation process. While the tool aims to focus in on the special capabilities of each actor, facilitating actors to self-nominate for tasks, and providing the opportunity to assess actors' changing interests in undertaking tasks, screening for unconscious biases in the process of self-nomination/allocation is nonetheless important.

As the Harvard podcast and other resources on unconscious bias teach us, we can hold biases about ourselves. We can hold beliefs and prejudices that limit what is possible about our own capabilities: what do we know, what skills or talents do we have, what are we capable of or not? Unleashing new (individual and collective) capabilities is a critical characteristic of the interactive innovation process.

Tool#2 in this handbook may be accompanied by an approach to assess unconscious biases that may influence the self-assigning/allocation of project tasks:

- Once the tasks have been brainstormed, invite participants to create a fictitious persona for each task/cluster of tasks based on the following questions (informed by the Harvard podcast):
 - » Who is an ideal candidate for this task (name, age, gender, location, ethnicity, profession/job etc.)
 - » How important are the following criteria for the person's capability to undertake this task?
 - Technical ability/'insider' knowledge?
 - Caring responsibilities/young children?
 - Introverted/extroverted nature?
 - Driven/ambitious/relaxed demeanour?
 - » Invite participants to discuss how important these criteria are in self-nominating for/being allocated to a task. According to the Harvard podcast, only the first criterion is legitimate: the others relate to personal/personality factors that are not deterministic of the capability to undertake a task. While it is important to note that some actors may not wish to undertake a task on the basis of their preferences, they should not feel limited by personal/personality characteristics.
 - » Facilitate a discussion about stereotypes, and how roles are perceived as suitable for some and not suitable for others. This discussion heightens awareness and reflexivity in how members of the multi-actor group think about their own and other's capabilities and possibilities.

2. Assessing Personas for Unconscious Bias

Tool#3 of this handbook supports a greater understanding of the actors involved/stakeholders engaged within the interactive innovation process, so that their knowledge is leveraged and their circumstances & needs understood. Personas are based on stereotypes, and while stereotypes can be useful for targeting project actions to some extent, biases must simultaneously be avoided. In addition to creating personas based on needs, circumstances etc. associated with a particular actor/stakeholder type, ask participants to build another persona – one who is the opposite to the stereotype portrayed in the original persona. The ‘opposite’ persona can be used as a communication tool to show ‘unusual suspects’ involved in and impacted by the interactive innovation process. This is particularly useful in a context where, according to some academic studies on non-participation in funded projects, the usual suspects tend to become involved. Optionally, the persona can be developed into a storyboard, where an unusual case of participation in interactive innovation is portrayed. As mentioned in the Harvard podcast, these stories can be used as ‘nudges’ to encourage greater participation – and more diverse participants – in interactive innovation.

3. Use of Reflective Diaries and Discussion Groups

Actors involved in interactive innovation – particularly those leading actions or tasks – can be encouraged to maintain a reflective diary. Accounts of their interactions, with different actors and stakeholders, detailing expectations and how they were/not met can be recorded. When unexpected/previously unknown needs & motivations are discovered, they can be added to the needs and motivations registers (Tool #5 and Tool #6).

A particularly successful initiative, as profiled in the Harvard podcast, took place as part of [Starbucks’ Third Place Initiative](#). An aspect of the initiative was to allocate dedicated periods of time for Starbucks staff to discuss unconscious bias in small groups. Resources, such as podcasts, are issued to staff and staff are encouraged to discuss the content. An increasing awareness of unconscious bias among Starbucks staff created positive, more inclusive culture change. This culture change extended beyond Starbucks staff to its customers, making the international chain more welcoming. The initiative at Starbucks is transferable to multi-actor teams of diverse members, supporting a more inclusive culture of knowledge/needs/perspective appreciation, which may be extended also to project stakeholders. The culture of curiosity described in the Harvard podcast – one that is inquisitive about and understanding of cultural difference – is crucial for innovation.

